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Title: Navigating Parenthood and Promoting Family Wellness: A Health Education Intervention for Parents of Exceptional Children Intervention

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Abstract:

Parents are challenged beyond challenges which includes having children with special needs who are fated to become totally dependent for life. However, with the SPED program offered to these children, maximizing their potential to become functional individuals in their families and communities makes raising them with ease possible. Parents on the other hand, play a big role in navigating the lives of these children but parents' self-care should not be neglected. Thus, equipping these parents with the right knowledge and skills through a health education intervention is deemed necessary. This qualitative phenomenological study aimed to explore the experiences of parents with special needs children across various domains of life. This study also underscores the importance of promoting responsible parenthood and promotion of family overall wellness. The sample size comprised of fifteen (11) participants who were mothers of special needs children currently enrolled in SPED Centers using an in-depth interview. Purposive sampling technique was utilized to collect samples. A semi-structured interview method was used to collect relevant data from the participants. Thematic analysis was adopted to analyze the data organized into themes. Five themes emerged namely parental response, process of acceptance, normalizing care, limited self-care, and advocacy. The results in this study highlight the challenges faced by the parents of special needs children, a basis in crafting a health education for parents in caring for their children with developmental disabilities and themselves.

Key words: Parenthood, Children with Special Needs, Developmental Disabilities

Introduction

Parenthood brings joy and happiness, however it may also pose challenges, starting from childbearing to childrearing and continues as the child grows and becomes fully independent. The shift to parenthood is a significant life event marked by major changes. While the arrival of a child is typically a joyful occasion, it can also impact interpersonal

Responsible parenthood requires being a capable and committed adult in raising children. It goes beyond providing for their basic needs and ensuring their well-being—it also involves guiding them toward becoming happy and responsible individuals (Valledor, 2023). Building on the **importance of responsible parenthood** in fostering **family wellness**, research underscores the role of **positive psychology, authoritative parenting, and informed caregiving strategies** in shaping healthy family dynamics. These principles are further reinforced by empirical findings that highlight how structured interventions can enhance parental well-being and strengthen family relationships.

A qualitative study on **Flourishing Families** illustrates how **mindfulness and character strengths** contribute to **parental resilience and emotional growth** (von Kraemer, 2023). Likewise, authoritative parenting has been found to **significantly reduce emotional distress and behavioral issues in children**, fostering a stable environment through warmth and responsiveness (Rothwell, 2024). Moreover, Makinano et al. (2022) affirm that parents demonstrate **strong awareness of their caregiving responsibilities**, emphasizing the necessity of **education and support systems** to empower them in fulfilling their roles effectively. This aligns with the **Filipino perspective on family well-being**, which encompasses multiple dimensions, including **lifestyle, financial security, strong relationships, effective parenting, and health**. Their study highlights how Filipino families prioritize **emotional bonds and ethical living** alongside economic security. Integrating this perspective reinforces the holistic nature of **responsible parenthood**, showing that caregiving extends beyond daily needs to fostering **long-term family contentment** and resilience (Chua, 2022).

But when parents must deal with children with disabilities, how can they practice responsible parenthood? While this journey may pose challenges, it is also a profoundly rewarding experience. A write-up of Reid identified certain difficulties in raising a child with a disability, such as the emotional strain and physical tiredness of providing care for the family (Reid, 2024). In addition, parents who are responsible for raising a child with special needs frequently struggle with intense feelings of blame and shame (Abimbola, 2023). Given the emotional and physical challenges of raising a child with a disability, as highlighted by Reid and Abimbola, parents often experience dilemmas in caregiving. This underscores the importance of collaborative care, as the responsibility of nurturing children with disabilities should not rest solely on parents. As the saying goes, “it takes a village to raise children”, and this is even more crucial when addressing developmental challenges in special children with disabilities.

Special children refer to individuals who require additional support due to physical, intellectual, emotional, or developmental differences. These children may have conditions such as **Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), Intellectual Disabilities,**

Cerebral Palsy, Down Syndrome, Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), Learning Disabilities, Emotional or Behavioral Disorders, and Speech and Language Disorders. Some may have physical impairments that affect mobility or sensory processing, while others may need specialized educational strategies to address cognitive challenges. Additionally, **gifted children**, while not classified as having disabilities, are sometimes considered part of the special needs spectrum because they require tailored educational approaches to nurture their exceptional abilities (Goldberg,2011; Beach, n.d.).

Within the broader spectrum of special-needs, Developmental Disabilities (DD) specifically impact cognitive, physical, and emotional growth. These disabilities specifically refer to those that persist throughout life and influence multiple domains of development. Included in this subset is Autism Spectrum Disorder, Intellectual Disabilities, Cerebral Palsy, Down Syndrome, and specific learning disorders. These disabilities may arise due to genetic factors, prenatal exposure to toxins or infections, complications during birth, or early childhood experiences. Individuals with developmental disabilities often face challenges related to communication, social interaction, motor skills, learning, and adaptive behavior (World Health Organization, 2012).

Developmental disabilities, while persistent throughout life, can benefit significantly from early intervention, tailored strategies, and comprehensive support. Addressing the unique needs of each child is crucial to maximizing their potential and fostering their growth. In this context, the implementation of the Special Education (SPED) Program marks a transformative shift, providing structured educational interventions that unlock latent abilities and enhance development. By equipping children with the skills to navigate daily life, contribute meaningfully to their families, and actively engage with their communities, SPED creates an environment where caregiving becomes not only manageable but also deeply enriching through the collaborative efforts of educators, therapists, and families.

Special Education in the Philippines

Special education refers to the development of instructional strategies, resources, and interventions designed to meet the needs of children with learning difficulties, giftedness, or learning differences. It plays a pivotal role in providing appropriate services to children with special needs, fostering their holistic development and enabling them to become independent and productive members of society (Proyalde, 2019).

In the Philippines, the SPED program was established as early as 1902, and over the decades, support for special education has remained largely positive. Various stakeholders, including non-governmental organizations and the government, have continuously responded to evolving demands and challenges with committed efforts.

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The government and private sector have made significant progress in ensuring equitable opportunities for children with special needs through various initiatives. One major legislative measure that has strengthened special education in the country is Republic Act 7277, also known as the Magna Carta for Persons with Disabilities. This Act promotes rehabilitation, personal growth, independence, and the inclusion of persons with disabilities into mainstream society. In alignment with this legislation, the Department of Education has mandated the establishment of Special Education Centers in every school district nationwide to facilitate the effective delivery of SPED services. Additionally, the said Republic Act guarantees that the SPED program enables children with special needs to experience optimal growth and development while meeting their educational requirements. It empowers administrators, educators, and collaborators with the necessary tools, knowledge, and support to transform this vision into a meaningful reality for these children (Llego, 2020).

However, while institutional frameworks and educational initiatives lay the foundation for inclusive learning, their true impact is realized through the active engagement of parents. The parents' dedication bridges the gap between policy and practice, ensuring that the principles of SPED are effectively translated into meaningful support for their children's unique needs. As primary advocates and caregivers, they play a fundamental role in ensuring that children with special needs receive the individualized attention and support necessary for their growth and development. Their involvement extends beyond the classroom, as they collaborate with educators and administrators to ensure tailored interventions, provide essential support at home, advocate for improved policies, actively participate in school activities, and nurture their children's emotional and social development (Lago, 2015).

Research underscores the significance of parental involvement in inclusive education. A study by Afolabi (2014) highlights how engaged parents contribute to learners' academic success by fostering a supportive environment. Another study conducted examining the academic participation and experiences of parents of children with special needs reveals the crucial role they play in their children's scholastic journey (Estojero, 2022). Parents not only facilitate opportunities for peer socialization but also navigate the complexities of raising children with unique needs, ensuring their holistic growth and development.

Recognizing and harnessing the critical role of parents in special education is essential for creating an inclusive and supportive learning environment for all students. Their active engagement strengthens the effectiveness of the SPED program, ensuring that children receive the individualized attention and care necessary for their success. As the primary navigators of their children's unique journeys, parents must be equipped with the right knowledge and skills to fulfill these responsibilities effectively. This study underscores the importance of amplifying their voices and providing the necessary support to empower them in their advocacy and caregiving efforts, fostering a system that acknowledges and reinforces their vital contributions.

Sustainable Development Goal 3 and the role of parents in Special Education goals

Sustainable Development Goal 3 (SDG 3) emphasizes ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being for all, particularly vulnerable populations such as children with special needs. Achieving this goal requires a holistic approach that extends beyond healthcare to encompass education, emotional development, and social inclusion (UNESCO, 2021). This study is essential because it highlights the crucial role of parents in advocating for comprehensive support systems that bridge healthcare and education. By equipping parents with essential knowledge, skills, and structured interventions, the study directly contributes to SDG 3's objectives of improving overall health and well-being.

Parental involvement has been shown to positively impact children's developmental progress and social integration. However, many caregivers struggle due to financial burdens, emotional fatigue, and a lack of institutional support (UNDP, 2020). Without adequate assistance, both parents and children face increased stress, leading to diminished caregiving effectiveness. This study seeks to address these challenges by promoting evidence-based interventions such as government-supported health education programs, SPED inclusion strategies, and community-driven support networks. By focusing on the well-being of caregivers, the study aligns with SDG 3's goal of ensuring a healthier, more equitable society where both parents and children can thrive.

The research also contributes to policy development, encouraging institutions and governments to recognize the significance of supporting parents holistically. Strengthening parental engagement in SPED advocacy fosters collaboration among families, educators, healthcare providers, and policymakers—ensuring sustainable solutions that enhance child development while safeguarding caregiver well-being (Philippine Commission on Women, 2019). Investing in parental support is not just a policy matter but a fundamental necessity in realizing SDG 3's vision of universal health and well-being.

Gender and Development and the Role of Parents in Special Education goals

This current study strongly aligns with Gender and Development (GAD) by addressing caregiving, parental roles, and gender-responsive health education. GAD emphasizes equity in caregiving responsibilities, recognizing that parents—especially mothers—often bear the emotional and physical burden of raising exceptional children (Philippine Commission on Women, 2013). By advocating for structured health education interventions, this research promotes shared responsibilities, ensuring both parents are equipped with essential caregiving knowledge and skills (UNESCO, 2021).

GAD also emphasizes empowerment, particularly for women as primary caregivers. This study supports this by providing strategies for caregiving, self-care, and advocacy,

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fostering gender-responsive health education that benefits both mothers and fathers (Department of Education, 2017). Additionally, the study highlights the need for institutional and community-based support, as gender-sensitive policies ensure equal access to

healthcare, education, and social services for parents of exceptional children (United Nations Development Programme, 2020).

Beyond individual caregiving, this research encourages parents to actively shape SPED programs and healthcare interventions, reinforcing gender-responsive governance. By normalizing caregiving roles, fostering shared responsibilities, and advocating for parental well-being, the researchers contribute to a gender-balanced approach that enables both parents to thrive while supporting their children (Philippine Commission on Women, 2019).

Research Gaps in parenting children with Disabilities

In the realm of education research, parental involvement has received considerable attention, particularly within mainstream schools. However, the role of parents in special education has been comparatively underexplored. Fewer researchers have focused on the role of parents in special education though the role of parents in schools has garnered increasing attention in educational research. and various research recommends the need for interventions to help parents in caring the special children even. This gap in research warrants further investigation, as parents play a pivotal role in shaping the educational experiences of children with special needs.

Despite growing awareness and advancements in special education and disability support, research on parenting children with disabilities still faces critical gaps. While existing studies highlight the challenges and resilience of parents, there remains a need for deeper exploration into their lived experiences, the effectiveness of support systems, and the societal barriers they encounter.

Here's few number of studies that would support this claim. One is the study of Wright and Taylor (2014) which highlighted that parental advocacy requires educating oneself, raising awareness and persistent efforts to secure services. Further in their findings, the parents of the children with disabilities should be equipped with resources, training and community support to strengthen their advocacy. Another study conducted in Manila, Philippines examined the challenges faced by parents of children with intellectual disabilities, particularly in navigating pre-vocational education. It highlighted the stress and concerns parents experience and the need for better support systems (Cabe, 2015). While Goldman and Burke (2017) highlighted the need for novel interventions to increase parent participation in Individualized Education Program meetings as well as studies focusing on parent involvement in other contexts for parents of children with disabilities.

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Another study conducted by Nomaguchi and Milkie (2020) emphasize that parental well-being is often overlooked, despite its profound impact on both parents and their children's development. While policymakers focus on ensuring that parents manage risks and opportunities for their children's future, they frequently neglect the emotional and psychological welfare of parents themselves. This oversight can have unintended consequences, as parental stress and well-being directly shape children's developmental outcomes.

Another study conducted in Isabela, Philippines, which explored the difficulties parents faced during the COVID-19 pandemic, including time management, teaching challenges, and the need for better educational resources (Degamo, 2021). In the same year, a study in conducted in Cagayan de Oro, Philippines, revealed that though families from diverse origins were given opportunities to be involved in school programs and activities, there were minimal opportunities on family education and training, few school policies were created and explained to the families, and not all families' needs, and state standards were met. The study recommends that families should receive adequate and relevant education workshops/trainings, regular family-teacher conferences; and increase the family involvement opportunities in all aspects (Presente, 2021).

Research indicates that parents of children with special needs often experience chronic exhaustion and depression, with limited resources for self-care compared to parents of typically developing children. Given the long-term demands of caregiving, sustaining their well-being is essential. Prior studies emphasize the importance of equipping parents with physical, emotional, and practical support to enhance their caregiving capacity.

In a nutshell, this study aims to support the creation of focused actions and recommendations for a better implementation of the SPED program. It underscores the importance of promoting responsible parenthood and promotion of family overall wellness, especially looking at the important roles of parents with children with special needs through a targeted health education intervention. Finally, it emphasizes proactive measures to enhance the health and overall, well-being of children with special needs by equipping parents with essential knowledge and skills to support their children effectively. The intervention program will also determine activities that will help the parents themselves, how to deal with challenges brought by caring for children with special needs without neglect on their own welfare, thus promoting family wellness.

Philosophical Underpinning

This study adopts a constructivist paradigm, a belief system commonly employed in qualitative research, to delve into the intricate fabric of embedded theories within factual observations. Constructivism posits that reality is a construct of the human mind, rendering it inherently subjective. In this context, the researcher actively constructs meaning from the phenomena under investigation, drawing upon both personal

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experiences and insights gleaned from study participants. By following a methodical sequence of logical steps, considering diverse participant perspectives, and employing rigorous data collection and analysis techniques, the constructivist approach sheds light on the nuanced human processes and experiences associated with special parenting conditions among parents of children with disabilities. Through this lens, we gain a deeper understanding of the phenomenon beyond mere sensory observations.

The foundation of this study rests upon the constructivist paradigm, which provides a lens through which to explore the intricate interplay between subjective reality and empirical evidence. By acknowledging that reality is shaped by individual cognition, constructivism invites us to consider the multifaceted dimensions of human experience. In this vein, our investigation focuses on the parenting conditions faced by parents of children with disabilities—a context ripe with complexities and nuances.

The constructivist framework guides our methodological choices. We view the research process as a series of deliberate steps, each contributing to a holistic understanding of the phenomenon. Key features of this approach include:

Subjective Reality: Constructivism posits that reality is not an objective entity but rather a product of human perception. By embracing subjectivity, we recognize that our understanding of parenting conditions is influenced by individual perspectives and interpretations.

Researcher as Meaning Maker: The researcher actively constructs meaning from the observed phenomena. Drawing upon personal experiences and engaging with study participants, we weave together a rich tapestry of insights. This participatory stance ensures that the researcher's subjectivity is an integral part of the inquiry.

Multiple Perspectives: The methodology accounts for the diverse viewpoints of participants. By engaging with parents of children with disabilities, we honor their unique narratives and consider the richness of their lived experiences.

Rigorous Data Collection and Analysis: Rigor is paramount. It will employ systematic data collection methods, such as interviews, observations, and document analysis. The thematic analysis allows us to distill patterns and themes from the raw data, revealing the essence of parenting conditions.

Theoretical Underpinning

Drawing from sociology, Albert Bandura's Theory of Self-Efficacy provides a valuable framework for understanding parental roles in caregiving. Self-efficacy refers to an individual's belief in their ability to execute specific behaviors that lead to desired outcomes. Several key tenets of this theory are relevant to parenting, particularly for those raising children with disabilities. 1) **Behavioral Agency:** Self-efficacy highlights an individual's capacity to influence events and exert control over their environment. In the context of parenting, this concept plays a pivotal role in shaping parental behaviors and coping strategies, allowing caregivers to respond effectively to their children's needs. 2) **Motivation and Well-Being:** Bandura's theory suggests that self-efficacy directly

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impacts motivation and overall well-being. Parents who perceive themselves as capable are more likely to engage in adaptive parenting practices, fostering positive developmental outcomes for both themselves and their children. 3) **Personal Accomplishment:** Self-efficacy contributes to a sense of accomplishment, as caregivers who feel efficacious approach the challenges of raising children with disabilities with resilience and determination. This belief in one's capabilities enhances coping mechanisms and strengthens parental engagement.

By intertwining the constructivist lens with Bandura's self-efficacy framework, this study seeks to illuminate the complexities of parenting conditions. Through rigorous inquiry, it aims to enhance understanding of the lived experiences of parents navigating the challenges of special needs caregiving. Ultimately, the research contributes to a more holistic view of theoretical phenomena, bridging theory and practice in the context of parenting and caregiving.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to explore the parent's experiences in caring for children with special needs in selected SPED Centers of Nueva Vizcaya from August to December 2024. Specifically, the study is geared for the following objectives:

1. To identify the experiences of parents in caring for children with special needs in the following areas:
 - 1.1 at home
 - 1.2 school
 - 1.3 community
2. To determine the pattern of experience of parents caring for children with special needs.
3. To craft a proposed intervention program for parents with special needs based on the findings.

Methodology

Research Design

A qualitative phenomenological design was utilized to describe the experiences of parents caring children with special needs particularly with developmental disabilities.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in the prime SPED Centers in Nueva Vizcaya namely Bayombong Central School, Solano East Central School and Bambang Central School Integrated SPED

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Center in which parents are bringing and fetching their children with special needs.

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Research Participants and sample

Initially, there were fifteen primary caregivers of children with special needs currently enrolled in SPED Centers, however, there was an attrition rate of 26% or four primary caregivers did not continue the second phase of the interview. With the 11 participants, data saturation was achieved. The researchers used purposive sampling with the following inclusion criteria: parenting a special child aging from 5-16 years old studying in the SPED centers, primary caregiver of the child and must be physically, psychologically, and emotionally stable. However, the participant will be excluded if he/she is parenting a special child in the mainstream.

Research Instruments

The researchers used a semi-structured interview guide made by the researchers as a tool to gather the data needed. Part 1 included the profile of the informants and Part 2 consisted of five (5) open-ended questions to gather data on their experiences in caring for their special child.

Data Gathering Procedures

The gathering of data started by giving a communication letter to the Division Office of Nueva Vizcaya particularly with the supervisor for Private Schools and SPED Centers. After which, the in-charge supervisor endorsed the researchers to the selected SPED Centers. The researchers sent a request letter addressed to the principal through the coordinators to have access to the list of parents with pupils of special needs prior to the actual gathering of data. After seeking approval, the researchers explained the scope and objectives of the study to the research locale. The researchers initially ask the assistance of the SPED teachers for the list of parents of children with special needs done to identify

the prospective participants of the study. The data gathering started from August to December 2024 in selected SPED Centers of Nueva Vizcaya. During the initial visit to the centers, the participants were approached personally by the researchers with the assistance of SPED teachers during a scheduled meeting in the school. For each participant, the researchers explained the purpose of the study and secured their consent to participate, sign the consent form before the interview. Upon obtaining consent from the participants, a face-to-face interview session was scheduled depending on the availability of the participants which will last not more than 30 minutes in a room provided for the interview. During the interview, there were 2 researchers with the participants performing with a script containing questions regarding the care through the guide questions. After noting down all the interview responses, the verbatim was presented to the respondents for verification or clarifications. Audio recorder, video and photos were taken during the interviews for documentation purposes with the consent of

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the participants. In addition, non-verbal cues such as body gestures and voice inflections were also observed since they may express the sincerity of responses of the participants. The researchers noted significant observations on the participants which can be used as supplementary data. Recorded data was transcribed and analyzed using thematic analysis. In this process, the responses will be summarized, and important points will be obtained. The themes and sub-themes on each research objective were formed and discussed on the findings of the study. The conduct of follow-up interview was done as necessary to verify and supplement data gathered. The interview sessions were held in the school while parents were waiting for their special children. The researchers and participants were stationed in an area free from noise to avoid distractions and away from others to secure the confidentiality of the data gathered.

Data Management and Analysis

The researchers had a one-on-one interview with the selected parents. A thematic approach was used to analyze the to be collected to explore the parents caring for children with special needs. All interviews and field notes were transcribed using the MS Word processing program. Saturation will occur when there are replications of data. The researchers ensured measures to enhance the methodological rigor of the research process to be conducted. In this way, the researchers understood better the experiences of parents in caring for their children with special needs.

Establishing Trustworthiness

The researchers were able to establish the study's trustworthiness through a process of verification rather than traditional measures by addressing the credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability.

Ethical Considerations

There is no conflict of interest as the study purely seeks to know and contribute to the understanding of the parent's experiences in caring for children with special needs. Furthermore, the study seeks to find a resolution to their concerns and for the betterment of their capability in providing care to their children. Consent will be taken from research participants prior to the conduct of the study. The participants will be assured that all information is confidential including their names. A pseudonym will be provided for each participant in the transcripts. All data were kept in a password encrypted file.

This consent will cover the conduct of interviews and the recording of photo, video, and audio materials. Participants will be asked to affix their signatures on the consent form, which will be provided in the Pilipino language. During this process, the terms of the agreement and the participant's role in the study will be clearly explained by the

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researcher. It will be emphasized that participation is entirely voluntary, and there will be no monetary compensation. Additionally, participants will be informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time they deem necessary. This approach ensures ethical and respectful engagement with all involved parties in the research endeavor.

In this research study, the researchers will employ robust measures to safeguard participant anonymity and protect sensitive data. Each participant will be assigned a pseudonym (a chosen nickname) to ensure their anonymity throughout the study. These pseudonyms will replace any direct reference to participants' real names. To manage data efficiently, the researchers will create unique codes for specific data points. This approach follows the "lock and key" principle, ensuring that only authorized personnel can decipher the coded information. The lead researcher will be solely responsible for handling and safeguarding the original hard copies of the pseudonym list and recording media (disks or USB drives). These materials will be stored securely to prevent unauthorized access. Documents obtained during interviews, including videos, audio recordings, and written forms, will be placed in individual envelopes. These envelopes will be securely sealed and stored in a designated box accessible only to the research team.

As per ethical guidelines, all interview materials will be retained for a period of five years. After this period, they will be systematically destroyed to maintain confidentiality. The researchers will refrain from photocopying or producing duplicates of any interview-related documents to further protect participant privacy.

By adhering to these rigorous protocols, the research team ensures both the integrity of the study and the confidentiality of participants' information.

The benefit of the study is to have an in-depth understanding of the perspective of parents of children with special needs to figure out a better approach towards their health and situation. Additionally, this can benefit by strengthening existing programs and implementation of new programs and implementation of new programs related to care of clients with special needs. Evaluating the need for improving the level of person-

centered care through healthcare providers' training, expand the provision of support services for parents, and improve professionals' knowledge and understanding of special needs of children and their parents. Although the study may trigger emotional outburst, personal space will be given to participants and the researchers will show calmness throughout the interview process.

However, there is known risks in the interview process because this can evoke stress and anxiety among participants, as they recall their experiences in caring for their special children, necessitating thoughtful measures to mitigate potential distress. But, to address this, the following strategies will be implemented. Prior to data collection, a pilot interview will be conducted. This preliminary session allows the researcher to identify any questions that may cause discomfort or anxiety. Based on insights gained from the pilot, necessary modifications to the interview questions can be made. At the outset of each interview, the researcher will provide a comprehensive briefing to participants.

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Participants will be informed that their involvement is entirely voluntary. They have the right to withdraw from the interview at any time without repercussions. Participants can choose not to answer specific questions if they feel uncomfortable. Additionally, the researchers will emphasize that there are no right or wrong responses to interview questions fosters an open and nonjudgmental environment.

Throughout the interview, an audio-video recording will be made for documentation and reference purposes. This ensures accuracy and transparency in data collection. For the purpose of having a safe interview environment, the researchers will conduct interviews within the school premises offers a secure setting. Researchers can utilize school facilities such as restrooms and the canteen, enhancing participant comfort. The interview sessions may take in the safety of their homes if the participants decide to be interviewed in his/her home.

As a precaution, the researcher will maintain a readily accessible list of contact numbers for nurses or therapists. This ensures timely assistance in case of any participant needs or emergencies. By adhering to these ethical guidelines, the research team aims to uphold participant well-being while gathering valuable insights.

After the conduct of the study, the important findings and recommendations of the will be disseminated in the research locale and other communities where there are parents of children with special needs, so that concerned stakeholders will be able to formulate feasible and achievable measures which will benefit the participants. Moreover, the study will be presented to conferences and forums, and eventually will look into its publication.

Results and Discussion

Five themes emerged from interviews of participants namely parental response, process of acceptance, normalizing care, limited self-care, and advocacy of SPED resources.

The first theme is on parental response. Among the 11 participants, most of them verbalized of the initially felt various parental responses from being sad, unhappy, worried about the condition and child's future .However, eventually accepted the child's condition and states a hope for a good future despite the disabilities. The concerns were raised, in terms of what they felt initially when they learned about the child's condition. Rose asserted:

" Malungkot ako kasi ung kalagayan niya (the child with Cerebral Palsy) at iniisip ko rin kung paano na maka survive kasi sakitin din siya"

The initial reaction every time someone get to know that a child that they will care of has a special need. Identified concerns include denial regarding what could have caused the

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condition, despite a good pregnancy. Dahlia, a mother of an Autism child stated

“Bakit ganito yung apo ko, maayos naman sa pag alaga yung mama niya nung buntis siya

Tulip, a mom of a child with Down Syndrome similarly and bluntly stated:

“*Noong una mam, in denial ako, kasi 25 years old lang ako at ganun yung kondisyon niya*”

Initial parental responses arise in various forms, as they get know a child with special needs. This could be a normal response as they begin to process the acceptance of the child's condition and looking into it as a blessing rather than a suffering. These responses may vary from one parent to another but an almost the same experience, enduring, it is moving on and embracing the reality of having a child with special needs compared to other children.

According to Heiman, T. (2021), parents of children with various disabilities often feel heightened emotions, predominantly negative ones such as loneliness and despair, throughout different stages of development. Nevertheless, these parents also conveyed optimistic hopes, belief, and assurance regarding the future. This could mean that these responses are important to recognize and should not be taken into aside because these are part of the whole process of becoming a parent along with disabilities.

The data implies that a negative initial parental response could be an important turning point towards a positive response for them to manage their child and provide the care needed.

The second theme is the Process of Acceptance. Acceptance is a deeply personal and transformative journey for parents and caregivers of children with developmental needs. The statements from Informants Rose, Sunflower, Orchid, Santan, and Informant 11 collectively illustrate the multifaceted nature of this process—one that involves emotional struggle, resilience, and, ultimately, a profound sense of understanding and

love. The gradual acceptance of the child's condition was evident in one participant statement: “*Tanggap ko na ganun ang anak ko, na siya(a child with Autism) ay regalo ng diyos sa akin*”-Sunflower

The process of acceptance often unfolds in stages, reflecting psychological models of adaptation such as Kubler-Ross's stages of grief (1969) and Turnbull et al.'s family adjustment framework (2015). Initially, caregivers may experience hesitation and uncertainty, as seen in Informant 11's reluctance before agreeing to an assessment. This aligns with research showing that denial or hesitation is common when families first encounter a child's developmental diagnosis (Hastings & Taunt, 2002).

Informant Sunflower's immediate acceptance, recognizing the reality of her child's condition while embracing responsibility, demonstrates active acceptance, a process in which caregivers acknowledge and integrate their child's needs into their lives (Hodge & Horner, 2020). This active acceptance is essential in fostering a nurturing environment

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that supports a child's growth, as highlighted by the American Academy of Pediatrics (2023) in their work on childhood development through caregiving interventions.

Meanwhile, Informant Rose and Santan exhibit normalization, where acceptance is deeply integrated into daily life. Rose's statement—*"I don't deny it—she is complete."*—suggests a shift toward viewing the child holistically rather than focusing on limitations. Research supports that normalization allows caregivers to move beyond grief and treat their child's condition as a fundamental part of life (Blacher & Baker, 2007). Additionally, recent studies on well-being-focused interventions (BMJ Open, 2023) emphasize the importance of fostering this normalization to enhance caregivers' emotional resilience.

Beyond personal adaptation, the acceptance journey is also shaped by emotional reappraisal and social dynamics. Informant Orchid's pride and gratitude reflect positive reappraisal, a process where caregivers reframe their child's developmental needs as a source of strength. Studies indicate that such reappraisal enhances resilience, allowing caregivers to cope effectively and find meaning in their experiences (Gupta & Singhal, 2005). The Springer study on Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (2021) reinforces this notion, showing how psychological flexibility and mindfulness can help caregivers shift perspectives and embrace acceptance.

Social acceptance is another crucial factor—Informant Santan's statement about leaving the acceptance of their child to others highlights societal attitudes toward developmental conditions. Families often encounter external judgments, making community support essential for fostering a positive caregiving experience (Kyzar et al., 2014). The AAP (2023) study underscores that responsive caregiving not only benefits children but also strengthens caregivers' mental well-being, reducing stress and reinforcing acceptance.

The findings of Shiju et. Al. (2023) also suggest that acknowledging a disability requires

a change in viewpoint and adapting to a different reality. Which could be the real end and beginning of the whole process, since it is only when you accept the reality that you are able to move forward.

The narratives of these caregivers reveal that acceptance is not a singular moment but an evolving process. It begins with hesitation, moves through realization, adaptation, and normalization, and ultimately reaches a place of pride and gratitude. Their experiences align with psychological theories and recent research, reinforcing that acceptance is deeply personal yet shaped by external support systems. By integrating insights from contemporary studies, we gain a deeper understanding of how caregivers navigate this complex journey—one defined by love, resilience, and an unwavering commitment to their children.

The third theme is geared on Normalizing Care **in Parenting**. This theme reflects the

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approach caregivers take in integrating children with developmental needs into everyday life without distinguishing them from their peers or siblings. The statements from Informants Dahlia, Orchid, Santan, and Informant 11 illustrate a shared perspective: caregiving is not about emphasizing differences but about fostering an environment where the child feels included, valued, and treated with fairness.

Normalization in caregiving refers to the process of integrating children with developmental needs into daily routines in a way that minimizes stigma and promotes inclusion. Informant Dahlia's statement—*"Caring for him is, of course, like caring for a young child."*—suggests an intuitive approach where caregiving is seen as a natural responsibility rather than a specialized task. This aligns with research emphasizing **responsive caregiving**, which highlights the importance of treating children with developmental needs in a way that fosters their emotional and cognitive growth (AAP, 2023).

Informant Orchid and Informant 11 reinforce this idea by emphasizing **equal treatment** within the family. Orchid's statement—*"There is no difference in how we treat him—we want everything to be fair, just like a normal upbringing."*—reflects the principles of **inclusive caregiving**, which research suggests can enhance a child's self-esteem and social development (BMJ Open, 2023). Similarly, Informant 11's approach of maintaining normal caregiving practices both at home and in school aligns with studies that advocate for **consistent caregiving environments**, which help children develop a stable sense of identity (Springer, 2021).

Normalizing care has significant psychological benefits for both the child and the caregiver. Studies indicate that when caregivers treat children with developmental needs as part of the family unit without excessive differentiation, it fosters **positive emotional development** and reduces feelings of isolation (Gupta & Singhal, 2005). Informant Santan's statement—*"It is all up to other people how they look at it."*—suggests an awareness of societal perceptions but also a commitment to maintaining a caregiving approach that prioritizes the child's well-being over external judgments.

Recent research on **the Nurturing Care Framework (AAP, 2023)** highlights how normalization contributes to **long-term developmental outcomes**. By ensuring that children receive care that is integrated into daily life rather than being framed as exceptional, caregivers help them build resilience and adaptability. Additionally, studies on **well-being-focused interventions (BMJ Open, 2023)** emphasize that caregivers who adopt normalization strategies experience lower stress levels and greater emotional stability.

The fourth theme is rooted to the caregiver's Limited Self-care. This theme is evident in the narratives provided by informants, where personal time and self-care routines are often minimized or neglected in favor of caregiving duties.

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Rose: *"I do all the household tasks at home, but I still make sure to watch over him. I prioritize him before myself. Despite all these obligations, I still fulfill my responsibilities as a grandmother."*

Sunflower: *"I take care of him before myself. I am able to take care of him. When he's asleep, of course, I get to take care of myself too, right? It's just about doing everything fast with the chores."*

Dahlia: *"When it comes to taking care of myself, I do get some time for it. But sometimes, I talk to others who can understand him. I don't do personal things like taking a bath if there's no one watching over him because I worry that something might happen."*

Informant Orchid: *"Monica is my priority. Getting her to school every day, helping her learn and enjoy life just like other children—that's what matters most. I don't even think about myself anymore."*

Informant 11: *"I no longer think about myself. I have no personal requests—only for my child, that's all. As long as it's for her well-being, I don't ask for anything else. I'm okay, as long as it's for her."*

The experiences of parents and guardians caring for children with developmental disabilities highlight a profound prioritization of their children's needs over their own well-being.

A recurring pattern in the statements is the informants' conscious choice to prioritize their children's well-being above their own. Informant Orchid emphasizes this sentiment by stating that she no longer thinks about herself, as her daughter's education and enjoyment of life are her primary concerns. Similarly, Informant 11 reflects a similar dedication, expressing that she no longer considers personal desires, as long as her child is taken care of.

These findings align with existing literature, which highlights the psychological and emotional toll of caregiving. Neff and Faso (2015) underscore the importance of self-compassion in mitigating stress and burnout among parents of children with developmental disabilities, demonstrating how caregivers often neglect personal well-being due to their overwhelming responsibilities.

Informants describe how limited time and constant supervision affect their ability to engage in basic self-care routines. Informant Rose and Informant Sunflower highlight the effort required to balance household tasks while maintaining vigilance over their child. Informant Dahlia also illustrates how personal routines, such as taking a bath, must be strategically planned around caregiving responsibilities due to concerns about safety.

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Research by Woodman et al. (2015) supports this observation, highlighting how caregiving demands often result in reduced time for self-care and increased psychological distress among parents. Their study suggests that caregivers must engage in structured routines to find brief moments for self-care.

Despite these challenges, some parents find ways to engage in self-care, albeit in constrained ways. Informant Sunflower acknowledges that she utilizes the moments when her child is asleep to care for herself but emphasizes the necessity of completing household chores efficiently. Informant Dahlia further highlights the importance of engaging with others who understand her child's condition, indicating that social interactions serve as an alternative form of emotional relief.

According to Kuhlthau et al. (2014), social support networks play a crucial role in alleviating stress among caregivers, providing an outlet for emotional well-being and improving resilience. Their study suggests that parents who receive community and peer support report better overall psychological well-being. The accounts of these parents underscore the necessity of external support systems, which could aid in redistributing caregiving responsibilities and fostering opportunities for self-care. Providing access to respite care, counseling services, and community support networks could help alleviate the emotional and physical burdens they carry (Schulz & Sherwood, 2008). These interventions can offer meaningful relief and ensure the well-being of both caregivers and their children.

The last theme is on the Advocacy for Support in Special Education Needs. Parents and caregivers of children with special education needs often emphasize the importance of adequate support systems to ensure holistic development. The need for comprehensive services—including educational resources, specialized therapy, and accessible assessments—plays a vital role in empowering both children and their families.

Informant Orchid asserts that "all the needs of SPED students should be fully provided," reinforcing the necessity for inclusive educational programs. Comprehensive special education services enable children to access individualized interventions tailored to

their specific needs. Research highlights that effective SPED programs incorporate adaptive teaching strategies, assistive technology, and well-trained educators to maximize student potential (McLeskey et al., 2017). Without sufficient resources, children with developmental disabilities face barriers that hinder their academic and social growth.

Informant Santan highlights a crucial gap in available services, stating that speech therapists are lacking in the province. Speech therapy is a fundamental component of intervention for children with communication challenges, facilitating language development and social interaction (American Speech-Language-Hearing Association, 2020). Advocacy for the establishment of specialized services in underserved areas is

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essential in bridging accessibility gaps and ensuring that children receive early intervention to improve their communication skills.

Informant 11 expresses the desire for free assessments, emphasizing the need for early identification of developmental concerns. Assessments play a key role in determining appropriate interventions and educational accommodations for children with special needs (Guralnick, 2017). Free or subsidized screenings enable families from various socioeconomic backgrounds to seek support without financial strain, reducing disparities in access to special education services.

The testimonies of caregivers reflect an urgent need for strengthened policies that expand SPED funding, increase the availability of specialists, and integrate free assessment programs. Advocacy efforts should focus on policy development that mandates accessible interventions, community outreach programs, and government support for special education services. Research supports the implementation of inclusive policies that prioritize early intervention and resource accessibility to foster improved outcomes for children with developmental needs (Smith et al., 2019).

Conclusion

The weight of caregiving can be overwhelming, filled with uncertainties and challenges. But the love and care of mother or a significant other from an immediate family member as the primary care givers knows no limit. Resilience, patience and sacrificial parenting is very evident to all participants.

Recommendation

This study recommends the inclusion of primary caregivers other than children with developmental disabilities. Furthermore, the utilization of a health education intervention program is highly recommended.

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Appendices

Informed Consent Form

This form is for parents of children with special needs in the SPED schools in their participation to the research project entitled **Navigating Parenthood and Promoting Family Wellness: A Health Education Intervention for Parents of Exceptional Children**.

Name of Researchers: **Benig, Sherylou A.,
Labangcoc, Marissa lyn A.,
Jontilano, Mary Rose C.**

Organizational Affiliation: Saint Mary's University
School of Health and
Natural Sciences
Department of Nursing

Information Sheet

You are being invited by researchers from Saint Mary's University to participate in their study on Navigating Parenthood and Promoting Family Wellness: A Health Education Intervention for Parents of Exceptional Children. You can take your time to decide whether to participate or not and you can ask questions any time for any word or concept in this form that you may not understand.

The purpose of this study is to explore the experiences of parents caring for children with special needs. The findings of the study will be used as a basis for a proposed Intervention Program for Parents of Exceptional Children.

This study involves the use of guide questions that you will answer during the interview. You are selected as participant because you are a parent of a child currently enrolled among the selected SPED schools. You are one among the 15 selected participants. Please be informed that there will be a conduct of individual interview with an estimated time of your participation in the study which will only take not more than 30 minutes. The scheduled interview will be done during your most convenient time in the school or in your homes and a follow up scheduled sessions will be done as needed. The interview shall be audio or video recorded and documented with your consent. If you do not wish to answer any of the questions, you may say so, and the interviewer will move on to the next question. Please be informed that your participation is voluntary, and you can withdraw any time without explanation. Your non-participation or withdrawal will not affect your standing as a parent of a child in the SPED school. No one else but the interviewer will be present unless you would like someone else to be there. The

information recorded is confidential, and no one except the researchers can access to the information documented during the interview. Rest assured that your privacy will be respected. Your identity will be anonymized by providing you with a number code instead of your name/email. Except for the researchers, no one will be able to identify you as respondent in this study. After the study is completed and finally submitted, all the data will be deleted for good, or all accomplished forms and records will be secured and kept to secure it in place.

There is known risk in your participation in the study because this can evoke stress and anxiety as you recall your experiences in caring for your special child. However, specific measures to allay your stress and anxiety will be implemented before, during and after

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the interview sessions. On the other hand, there is no direct benefit to you either. You shall not receive any payment for your participation nor any reimbursements. However, you will be contributing to the proposed health intervention program and this may be beneficial to the parents of SPED schools, and future references.

The results of this study may be disseminated within the respected SPED school your son or daughter is currently enrolled in. Also, the study may be submitted for publication in national or international journals. For any matter concerning this study, you can contact Sherylou A. Benig with mobile number 09175909737 or email: sbenig@smu.edu.ph.

This study is funded by Saint Mary's university through the Wealth program of the faculty research. The intellectual property of the research belongs to the university and the researchers will always be recognized as the authors.

This study is approved by the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) at Saint Mary's University, Ponce Street, DMM, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya with cellphone number: 09177053041 and email: reb@smu.edu.ph.

Certificate of Consent

I have read the foregoing information, or it has been read to me. I have had the opportunity to ask questions about it and any questions I have asked have been answered to my satisfaction. I consent voluntarily to be a participant in this study.

Print Name of Participant: _____

Signature of Participant: _____

Date: [MM/DD/YYYY]

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

Part 1: Profile of the Respondents. Instruction: Please check your answer; otherwise, supply your answer.

Age: _____ Gender: ___Male ___Female

Educational Attainment: _____

Marital Status: ___Single ___Married ___Widow

Occupation: _____

Primary Care Giver: ___Yes ___No

Child's Age: _____

Case of his/her special child: _____

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Part 2: Interview Guide Questions

1. How do you feel when you were informed that your child is with special needs?
2. Can you describe your experiences in caring for your child with special needs?
 - i. At home
 - ii. School
 - iii. Community
3. How do you keep your child with special needs?
 - i. At home
 - ii. School
 - iii. Community
4. How do you keep yourself in managing your child with special needs?
 - i. At home
 - ii. School
 - iii. Community
5. What are your needs in caring your child with special needs?

Thank you so much for your participation. God Bless ☺

CURRICULUM VITAE

I. General information	
Name Sherylou A. Benig	

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BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

Date of birth: November 8, 1983	
Contact number: 0917-590-9737	
Email address: sbenig@smu.edu.ph	
Address: Purok 3, Pacursa St. Brgy. Magsaysay, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya	

2 x 2 PICTURE

Affiliation	Name of Institution: Saint Mary's University
	Name of Department: School of Health and Natural Sciences- Nursing
	Position: Department Head
	Specialty (Course and Year for Students):

II. Educational Background

<i>Name of Institution:</i>	<i>Course/Degree:</i>	<i>Year/s attended:</i>
Saint Louis University	Ph. D in Nursing	August 2017-December 2021
Saint Mary's University	MS in Nursing	2005-2009
Saint Mary's University	BS in Nursing	2000-2004

III. Research Related Training within the last 5 years

<i>Name of Course:</i>	<i>Offered by:</i>	<i>Actual Date:</i>
5 th International Conference on Qualitative Research in Nursing, Health, and Social Sciences	Saint Louis University	December 4-5, 2024

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19 th Regional Nursing Research Congress: "Imbibing a Research Culture in Nursing Practice"	UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER Saint Louis University	April 18, 2018
Research Seminar: "Crossing the Bar in Research among Nurses"	Region 2 Trauma and Medical center	
1 st International Nursing Education, Practice and Research Conference	NEPhRA Guild	August 25-26, 2017
IV. Description of Past and Present Research-Related Involvement that is Aligned with the Proposed Research Topic		
<p>The researcher was deployed to SPED Centers every 2nd Semester of the School Year with the Course NCM117 RLE following up BSN 3 students. With the immersion they have in this area, the researcher observed difficulties of parents of special needs. Hence, would want to navigate more on the unseen challenges and envisions to create interventions to these problems through programs.</p>		
Name and Signature: Sherylou A. Benig	Date: July 23, 2024	

CURRICULUM VITAE

I. General information

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Name : Marissalyn A. Labangcoc UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER	2	
Birthday : September 2, 1980		
Contact number: 09531864311		
Email address: marissalynlabangcoc@gmail.com		
Address: Buliwao, Quezon, Nueva Vizcaya		
x 2 PICTURE		
Affiliation	Name of Institution: Saint Mary's University	
	Name of Department: Nursing	
	Position: Nursing Instructor	
	Specialty (Course and Year for Students): Maternal and Child Nursing Nursing Research	
II. Educational Background		
<i>Name of Institution:</i>	<i>Course/Degree:</i>	<i>Year/s attended:</i>
Saint Mary's University	BSN	1997-2001
Saint Mary;s University	MSN	2006-2009
III. Research Related Training within the last 5 years		
<i>Name of Course:</i>	<i>Offered by:</i>	<i>Actual Date:</i>
Training Workshop on Writing for Publication	SMU URC	February 27, 2024
NCM (Area: SPED) Related Learning Experience	SMU	

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UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER	
IV. Description of Past and Present Research-Related Involvement that is Aligned with the Proposed Research Topic	
Exploring the Maternity Experience of Women with Physical Disabilities- The study aims to determine measures to improve maternity care among women with physical disabilities. Women with physical disabilities belong to clients with special needs in healthcare.	
Name and Signature: MARISSA LYN A. LABANGCOC	Date: JULY 29, 2024

RESUME of

MARY ROSE C. JONTILANO, RN, MSN, Professional Teacher

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UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER ^{Mobile #: 0916 308 2516}

PERSONAL INFORMATION

Date of Birth: September 8, 1970 Age: 53
Civil Status : Married Height : 5 feet Weight :
58kgs

EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

POST-
GRADUATE

- 1. Ph. D. Nursing (on-going Dissertation)**
- 2. Masters of Science in Nursing**
Major in Maternal and Child Nursing, at Saint Mary's University,
Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines October 19, 2009

GED 210 (Differential Psychology) 3units
GED 207 (Educational and Psychological Testing) 3 units

COLLEGE

- 1. Bachelor of Science in Nursing** at University of Santo Tomas,
Sampaloc, Manila, Philippines, March, 1991
- 2. Principles and Strategies of Teaching** at Saint Mary's
University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines, SY 1998-1999

Secondary

Saint Mary's College, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines, March,
1987

Primary

Saint Mary's College, Central Department, Bayombong, Nueva
Vizcaya, Philippines, March 1983

others

Live-in Caregiver Skill Development Program
Fil-Canadian Training and Development Center for Caregivers,
Guadalupe, Makati City, Philippines

Examinations Taken

1. Licensure Examination for Teachers (Philippine Regulation Commission)
September 1999
License #: 0632829

2. Nursing Licensure Examination (Philippine Regulation Commission) June 1991
License
#: 0186187

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3. Commission on Graduates of Foreign Nursing Schools (CGFNS), November 7, 2007, passed

4. IELTS: July 14, 2007, band 7

5. Civil Service, 1999

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE:

2016-current year	Lecturer/Researcher/ Clinical Instructor, Saint Mary's University- School of Health Sciences
2010-2016	*Member of Institutional Research of Saint Mary's University-School of Health Sciences *Nursing Research Coordinator/ Instructor/Adviser
June 2008 to 2009	Level 2 Clinical Coordinator Saint Mary's University-School of Health Sciences
June 2003 to 2008	Lecturer/ Clinical Instructor, Saint Mary's University, School of Health Sciences
March 1998-1999	Volunteer Nurse, Nueva Vizcaya, Provincial Hospital, Bambang, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines
March 1994-1995	Volunteer Nurse, Dupax District Hospital, Dupax Del Norte, Philippines
May 1992-June 1993	Staff nurse, Alferos Hospital, Olongapo City, Philippines

Trainings and Seminars attended for the last 4 years

Date	Title	Place
January 16-17, 2016	Seminar-Workshop on Preparing a Thesis	Saint Mary's University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya
June 24, 2016	Orientation on Research policies and itinerary	Saint Mary's University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya
February 16, 2017	School of Health and Natural Sciences Week: "Missio et Excellentia, the Difference that We Make"	Saint Mary's University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

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UNIVERSITY RESEARCH CENTER		
February 16, 2017	School of Health and Natural Sciences Week: "Missio et Excellentia, the Difference that We Make"	Saint Mary's University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya
March 8, 2017	2017 Research Dissemination Forum and Research Exhibit Caravan: "R1HRDC Bolstering People's Quality of Life Through Health Research and Dissemination"	University of Northern Philippines Vigan City, Ilocos Sur
March 25, 2017	18 th Regional Nursing Research Congress: "Upholding Integrity in Research: Principles and Responsibilities in Scientific Writing and Publication"	Saint Louis University, Baguio City
April 28, 2017	Research Seminar on "Selecting the Right Approach: A Review of Research Methods"	Don Mariano Marcos Memorial State University –South La Union Campus, Agoo, La Union
May 29, 2017	Lecture-Forum on "Doing Qualitative Research in a Community Setting"	Saint Mary's University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya
July 16, 2017	Scientific Session: "Nursing Specialization in Clinical Practice"	Saint Louis University, Baguio City
July 16, 2017	8 th Jesusa B Lara Lecture Series "Optimizing Translational Research in Nursing"	Saint Louis University, Baguio City
August 11, 2017	Research Seminar: "Knowledge Translation: Initializing and Ingraining into Practice"	Saint Louis University, Baguio City

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August 25, 2017
1st International Nursing Education, Practice and Research Conference

Crown Legacy Hotel, Baguio City

December 19, 2017
Research Seminar: "Crossing the Bar in Research among Nurses"

Veterans Regional Hospital, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya

January 22, 2018
2018 PNAAL Balik Turo: "Ideas and thoughts- Nursing Innovations that Inspire"

Saint Louis University, Baguio City

April 28, 2018
19th Regional Nursing Research Congress: "Imbibing a Research Culture in Nursing Practice"

Saint Louis University, Baguio City

August 16, 2019
2019 Career Guidance Week Celebration: "Follow a Guide, Tag a Career, Like the Future"

Aritao National High School, Aritao, Nueva Vizcaya

August 27, 2021
Ethnography Research Design and Grounded Theory via Zoom meeting

PNRSI Baguio-Benguet Cells Webinar Series 2

April 18, 2022
Webinar on Integration of Transcultural Nursing in Philippine Nursing Education via Zoom

College of Nursing, University of the Philippines Manila

December 8-9, 2022
Training on Packaging Research Projects for Journal Publications

Isabela State University-Cauayan Campus Participant

February 22-24, 2023
3rd International Conference on Cultural Studies

Saint Mary's University, Bayombong, Nueva vizcaya Philippines participant